

Template for Law/SHS Bibliographic Research Record

Established by Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy¹ for collaborative bibliographic research

January 2026

Context

This template has been established in 2020 by Dr Aurélie Mahalatchimy in order to share and avoid duplicating the work related to bibliographic research, especially in the context of collaborative research. It has been particularly useful when managing multiple research projects, involving different individuals working on similar or identical research topics.

Completing the form allows the initial researcher or one of their colleagues with whom the completed form is shared to expand or update the previous series of bibliographic searches on the same subject at a later date.

Widespread use and open access to completed forms would save researchers time when they begin working on a topic for which bibliographic research has already been conducted. This is part of open science for the benefit of the scientific community.

Acknowledgements

The initial template established in 2020 has been used from 2021 with my collaborators, Luc-Sylvain Gilbert, Edouard Habib, Eloïse Gennet, Auxane Delage, Valentin Roby, and Adrien Bottacci, in the context of the EuroGCT project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (GA No 965241), and I-BioLex (ANR-20-CE26-0007-01), and Organact (ANR-22-CE41-0012) research projects funded by the French National Agency for Research. I deeply thank them for their useful feedback.

Guidance for completing the template

This template should be filled in when doing bibliographic research on a specific research topic.

1/Complete and adapt the template to your needs

The template should be renamed in order to include the topic of bibliographic research.

The list of bibliographic databases may be supplemented or adapted (e.g., by order of priority) according to the needs of the research. The list provided below has been established from the law discipline.

Where it is known from the beginning that the bibliographic research is conducted for collaborative purposes and where the collaborators are known, it is advised to agree on the list of bibliographic databases to be consulted, and possibly to order them by priority.

¹ Permanent Researcher in law at the French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS, chargée de recherche), Law Faculty, Aix Marseille Univ, CNRS, DICE, CERIC, Aix-en-Provence, France.

2/For each bibliographic database listed on the template, the following general information should be provided.

- Name of the researcher: *who is conducting the bibliographic research*
- Date of the research: *when is the bibliographic research conducted*
- Last update: *if relevant, when is the update of the bibliographic research conducted*
- Topic of the research: *what is the topic of the bibliographic research conducted*

2/When completing the template, the following information should be provided regarding each bibliographic database used.

- **Research method:** *to explain here the research method*
 - o Mainly what is/are the exact keyword(s) used and how have they been used (« » ; * ; AND ; OR...). It may be relevant to agree on the choices of keywords with the collaborators, if they are known.
 - o Please be as precise as possible. This is all the more important than not all databases will support Boolean research (for instance no "*" on Dalloz), or not all databases will offer the same advanced research options (some will offer to select a time frame from the beginning, others will only have it as a filter of results after; some will offer to specify that you want only the results where the keyword appears in the title or abstract, some will not have this option and you may have to do it by yourself...)
 - o To adapt the language (French, English, ...) to the chosen database and to write the keywords in each language
 - o To remember using "*" which can be very helpful, and if so, to mention it.
- **First number of results from the database:** *this is the first number of results provided by the bibliographic database where the research is conducted.*
- **Exclusion criteria:** *criteria used to exclude results irrelevant to the research conducted*
 - o Any further filter that is added after obtaining the first number of results. For example, it can be a filter provided by the search functions of the database, or a relevance criterion that you have in mind when going through all the results (e.g., exclusion of legislation to target academic literature only)
- **Final number of selected results:** *final number of results considered relevant to the research that is conducted on the bibliographic database.*

3/ Compile your selected papers in a library for analyses purposes

Papers selected in the last columns of the template should be compiled in a shared library (Zotero, Endnote,...) for collaborative works.

TOPIC OF RESEARCH

1.	Phase I- Law bibliography databases.....	4
1.1.	Law bibliography databases in French.....	4
1.1.1.	Dalloz.....	4
1.1.2.	Lexbase.....	4
1.1.3.	Lexis 360 Intelligence (previously LexisNexis) (Revues).....	5
1.1.4.	Lextenso (Revues).....	5
1.1.5.	Navis (Revues).....	6
1.1.6.	Bibliothèque numérique en droit de la santé (BNDS).....	6
1.1.7.	Le Doctrinal.....	7
1.1.8.	Lamyline Reflex.....	7
1.2.	Law bibliography databases in English.....	8
1.2.1.	HeinOnline.....	8
1.2.2.	Westlaw (Journals).....	8
1.2.3.	Law Review Commons.....	9
1.2.4.	Oxford Scholarship Online : Law.....	9
2.	Phase II- SHS bibliography databases.....	11
2.1.	Cairn revues.....	11
2.2.	OpenEdition Journals.....	11
2.3.	Brill revues - Archives ISTEEX.....	12
3.	Phase III- Other/more general bibliography databases.....	13
3.1.	Wiley Online Library.....	13
3.2.	Cambridge University Press Revues - Archives ISTEEX.....	13
3.3.	De Gruyter revues - Archives ISTEEX.....	14
3.4.	JSTOR.....	14
3.5.	ScienceDirect – SD.....	15
3.6.	Springer Nature - ebooks et revues - Archives Istex.....	15
3.7.	Web of Science.....	16
3.8.	PubMed.....	16
3.9.	Google Scholar.....	17

1. Phase I- Law bibliography databases

1.1. Law bibliography databases in French

1.1.1. Dalloz

Name of the researcher: *who is conducting the bibliographic research*

Date of the research: *when is the bibliographic research conducted*

Last update: *if relevant, when is the update of the bibliographic research conducted*

Topic of the research: *what is the topic of the bibliographic research conducted*

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.2. Lexbase

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.3. Lexis 360 Intelligence (previously LexisNexis) (Revues)

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.4. Lextenso (Revues)

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.5. Navis (Revue)

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.6. Bibliothèque numérique en droit de la santé (BNDS)

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.7. Le Doctrinal

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.1.8. Lamyline Reflex

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.2. Law bibliography databases in English

1.2.1. HeinOnline

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.2.2. Westlaw (Journals)

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.2.3. Law Review Commons

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

1.2.4. Oxford Scholarship Online : Law

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

2. Phase II- SHS bibliography databases

2.1. Cairn revues

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

2.2. OpenEdition Journals

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

--	--	--	--

2.3. Brill revues - Archives ISTEK

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3. Phase III- Other/more general bibliography databases

3.1. Wiley Online Library

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.2. Cambridge University Press Revues - Archives ISTEK

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

--	--	--	--

3.3. De Gruyter revues - Archives ISTEK

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.4. JSTOR

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.5. ScienceDirect – SD

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.6. Springer Nature - ebooks et revues - Archives Istex

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.7. Web of Science

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.8. PubMed

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library

3.9. Google Scholar

Name of the researcher:

Date of the research:

Last update:

Topic of the research:

Research method	Number of results	Exclusion criteria	Final number of results to be included in library